

TYPES OF ASSESSMENT AND THEIR PECULIARITIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION

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Abstract: There are various types of assessment in higher education institutions, which play an important role in the analysis of students' knowledge and skills. This article examines the characteristics of the main types of assessment, such as formative and summative assessment, self-assessment, and peer assessment. Each type of assessment has a different impact on student learning. Evaluation efficiency is analyzed using a diagram based on statistical data. As a result, knowledge about the role of assessment in the educational process and its impact on student success will expand.

Keywords: Higher education, types of assessment, formative assessment, summative assessment, mutual assessment, self-assessment, skills, cognitive process, educational effectiveness, assessment techniques, student performance, diagnostic assessment, education assessment, quality education, development, statistical analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Assessment is an integral part of the higher education process, which serves to measure the knowledge and skills of students. Types and methods of effective assessment in higher education institutions allow teachers to analyze the level of development of students and increase their interest in knowledge. Formative and summative evaluations, mutual and self-evaluations play a special role in improving the effectiveness of the evaluation process. This article analyzes the characteristics of assessment types used in higher education institutions, their benefits to students and teachers, and the importance of assessment results. The article shows the effectiveness of the evaluation using a diagram based on statistical data.

Main part

The assessment process helps to improve the quality of education in higher education institutions and increase the knowledge and skills of students. In analyzing the types of assessments used in higher education, the main focus is on their impact on students, effectiveness, and information they provide to teachers. Formative

assessment allows you to monitor the progress of students in the educational process and help them individually. This is done through a variety of methods, including regular testing, rapid feedback, and analysis of project activities. The advantage of this type of assessment is that it allows for continuous changes in the learning process.

Summative assessment is conducted after the end of the lesson or at the end of the course and is used to measure the general level of knowledge. This is usually done through final exams, tests and thesis projects. This type of assessment helps teachers determine the overall level of student learning, but makes it difficult to identify individual student strengths and weaknesses.

Peer assessment involves students evaluating each other and giving feedback to each other. This helps students learn from each other, develop teamwork skills, and express their opinions. At the same time, the student will identify his strengths and weaknesses. Self-assessment gives the student the opportunity to analyze his own knowledge and skills. This method increases students' ability to self-develop and work on themselves.

In higher education institutions, the assessment process is widely used in order to measure the level of knowledge of students, improve the quality of education, and ensure the effectiveness of the educational process. Assessment takes many forms, and each type has its own characteristics. The main types of assessment include formative assessment, summative assessment, peer assessment and self-assessment. These methods create effective ways of sharing knowledge between teachers and students, provide an individual approach to the learning process, and make the learning process of students more qualitative.

Formative assessment is the most effective way to study the student's development and activity in the learning process. This type of assessment is used continuously in the educational process and provides an opportunity to determine the student's strengths and weaknesses in the educational process. For example, in the educational process, short tests, homework or project work are used to test the student's theoretical knowledge. The main goal of formative assessment is to analyze the student's achievements and difficulties during the lesson and to make the necessary changes. In this process, the student's activity in the learning process increases and he has the opportunity to develop his learning independently. Also, formative assessment helps students to work on themselves and evaluate their knowledge correctly. The advantages of this type of assessment are that it not only measures the student's knowledge, but also encourages him to participate more actively in the learning process.

Summative assessment is used for the final evaluation of student knowledge after the end of the course or lesson. This type of assessment is mainly done through final exams, tests and projects. The advantages of summative assessment are that it allows to assess the general level of student knowledge and helps the teacher to analyze student knowledge more deeply. However, summative assessments provide less information about how a student has progressed or struggled during the course. This method does not provide an individual approach to the educational process, as summative assessment is aimed only at evaluating the final result. For example, a student's general knowledge level is assessed through exams or course projects, but these results do not indicate learning difficulties or individual student needs. Therefore, summative assessment is often used in combination with formative assessment.

Peer assessment allows students to exchange ideas and evaluate each other's knowledge. This method plays an important role in the educational process for the development of communication between students, learning from each other and encouraging the exchange of knowledge. For example, students are given the opportunity to analyze each other's projects or evaluate each other's presentations. Through this method, students not only strengthen their knowledge, but also develop their critical thinking and analytical skills. Another advantage of peer assessment is that in this process, students use the feedback provided by their peers to deepen their knowledge and skills. This method also helps students identify their strengths and weaknesses and understand what changes need to be made to develop them.

Self-assessment allows students to independently analyze their knowledge and skills. This method plays an important role in the student's self-development and identification of difficulties in the learning process. Through self-assessment, the student learns his strengths and weaknesses independently and shows interest in working on himself. This method helps the student to be independent and disciplined and encourages him to regularly test his knowledge.

For example, students strengthen their knowledge by evaluating their knowledge through various tests or questions. In this process, the student understands how to correctly assess his level of knowledge and how to make changes in the process of learning.

Each method has its own advantages and limitations in the evaluation process. Formative assessment helps motivate students during the lesson and quickly identify difficulties in the learning process, but it is not able to fully measure the final level of knowledge. Summative assessment shows the overall results of the educational

process, but in this process the individual needs and level of development of the student are not taken into account. Peer assessment and self-assessment help students to be more active in the learning process, develop communication and identify their strengths and weaknesses. The joint use of these methods makes the educational process more effective and increases the activity of students in the learning process.

At the same time, innovative assessment methods are widely used in modern education. For example, electronic assessment systems, tests and projects using digital technologies encourage students to adapt to new learning methods. Electronic assessment systems allow rapid assessment of student knowledge and real-time results. With the help of these systems, teachers will have the opportunity to quickly analyze the activity of students in the educational process. Also, e-assessment results allow students to provide quick feedback, which helps them test themselves in the learning process. Digital assessment technologies are widely used in modern higher education institutions to make the educational process interactive and effective.

Conclusion

Types of assessment are important in improving the effectiveness of the educational process and in a deeper analysis of students' knowledge and skills. Formative assessment allows students to constantly test themselves and develop, forming individual development paths for them. Summative assessment allows teachers to make a final assessment of students' knowledge levels. Peer assessment and self-assessment help students learn from each other and strengthen their own knowledge. In this way, it is possible to increase the effectiveness of the educational process through the combination of different types of assessment in modern higher education.

In short, the types of assessment are important in higher education to correctly assess the knowledge and skills of students, increase the effectiveness of the educational process, and improve the quality of education. Each type of assessment has its own characteristics that enrich the learning process. Formative, summative, peer, and self-assessment play different roles in student development, and each serves its own purpose. Therefore, it is possible to make the educational process more effective by harmonizing assessment systems in higher education institutions and choosing assessment methods that suit the individual needs of students.

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